

Securing Authentication and Authorization in Computing Continuum

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Abstract

This research paper presents the experience of the authors in implementing protocols for authentication and authorization, along with secure key exchange mechanisms for accessing remote resources within a computing continuum scenario. The implementation encompasses a comprehensive security framework designed to facilitate secure access control and cryptographic key management across resource-constrained **Internet of Things (IoT)** devices, edge nodes, and cloud platforms, addressing the unique challenges of distributed computing environments. In particular, this implementation integrates the **Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ACE)** framework, **Ephemeral Diffie-Hellman Over COSE (EDHOC)** protocol, and **Object Security for Constrained RESTful Environments (OSCORE)** protocol. The proposed model combines **ACE** for authentication and authorization, **EDHOC** for secure key exchange, and **OSCORE** for message security. By facilitating the delegation of authorization management to less constrained trusted hosts, the work optimizes resource utilization while maintaining robust security across the entire continuum. **KEYWORDS:** ACE Framework, OAuth, EDHOC, OSCORE, IoT

1 Introduction

This work proposes an authentication and authorization mechanism for **IoT** resource-constrained devices, delivering a secure and efficient security solution for constrained environments. Its comprehensive and standardized approach sets it apart from other proposals, fostering broader adoption and facilitating the seamless expansion of connected devices.

The integration is particularly innovative because it combines lightweight protocols specifically designed for IoT constraints while maintaining robust security properties. Unlike other proposals, it provides a complete solution for authentication, authorization, and secure communication that is both scalable and efficient for constrained environments. Furthermore, the project utilizes **Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)**'s RFC protocols for constrained devices, which require minimal code, memory footprint, and power consumption compared to traditional protocols like **Transport Layer Security (TLS)/Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS)**.

The objectives focus on developing a security model integrating the ACE framework with EDHOC and OSCORE profiles. ACE provides comprehensive IoT security, EDHOC offers lightweight key exchange, and OSCORE ensures end-to-end security for **Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP)** messages. The document structure includes technology overview, solution design and methodology, implementation testing, and conclusions.

2 State of the Art

The **ACE** framework [1] extends OAuth 2.0 to provide authentication and authorization in constrained **IoT** environments, utilizing **Proof of Possession (PoP)** tokens and defining security

profiles for diverse devices. The **EDHOC** protocol [2] is a lightweight Diffie-Hellman key exchange mechanism designed for resource-constrained environments, providing mutual authentication, forward secrecy, and identity protection while minimizing bandwidth usage. Moreover, **OSCORE** [3] secures CoAP communications using **CBOR Object Signing and Encryption (COSE)**, ensuring end-to-end security and demonstrating superior performance over DTLS in terms of overhead, round-trip time, memory usage, and energy efficiency [4]. Finally, **CoAP** [5] is a specialized UDP-based web transfer protocol designed for resource-constrained IoT devices, that provides REST-like functionality similar to **Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)** but with minimal overhead and built-in security through **DTLS**.

3 Related Work

While security research on these technologies is active [6] these researches focus on lower level aspects such as bootstrapping and secure network onboarding, but it is difficult to find researches regarding the protection of application level interactions through authentication and authorization (resource access control). In this line, the work in [7] studied the performance of **OSCORE** with **Static Context Header Compression and fragmentation (SCHC)** compression for enabling the IP stack in LPWANs, and the work in [8] proposed the use of **EDHOC** in LoRaWAN for session key update. Closely related work is found in [9] on the development of a CoAP-based access control framework, but it does not follow any standardisation and does not consider encryption and secure device provisioning.

Key security requirements for continuum operations include access policies, authentication, and data protection. An integrated solution addressing these aspects could significantly improve security in distributed computing environments. To our knowledge, no work has evaluated the ACE-OAuth standard across the entire computing continuum. This study presents the first performance evaluation of the ACE-OSCORE-EDHOC profile in this context, offering insights into secure data sharing from IoT devices to edge nodes and cloud platforms.

4 Proposed Solution

The proposed solution integrates the ACE framework with EDHOC and OSCORE protocols to provide secure authentication, authorization, and protected data sharing among IoT-Edge-Cloud devices for the computing continuum. This combination addresses a "zero-touch" constrained configuration among IoT-Edge-Cloud devices where authenticated and authorized operations can be performed. In particular, these protocols include the roles of the **Client (C)**, which is a constrained device deployed at the edge that consumes and processes data from IoT devices, the **Resource Server (RS)**, which is an IoT device that can act as a sensor or actuator, and the **Authorization Server (AS)**, which is hosted in the cloud and is assumed not to be constrained. Also, another important element is the access token, which allows the C to consume a resource from the RS. This access token is generated by the AS, which acts as a trusted third party and controls if a specific C can consume resources from the RS. All communications between the different roles use CoAP [10].

4.1 Client to Authorization Server Communication

The first step to obtaining an access token is establishing a secure context between C and AS to protect communication, achieved by running the EDHOC and OSCORE protocol between them.

Once the EDHOC session is completed, C and AS establish an **OSCORE** Security Context, which provides authenticated and secure **CoAP** communication between them. Once the secure channel is established, C makes a CoAP POST request to a specific endpoint on the AS, which must be the `/token` endpoint. Also, in this POST request, the client specifies its credentials by reference, such as a hash of an X.509 certificate. Indeed, it is expected that the client will be able to identify its credentials by reference as the AS is expected to have obtained the specific credentials during a prior registration or secure establishment of the client. Furthermore, the POST request to the `/token` endpoint in the AS and the corresponding response may include a **Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR)** object containing information related to the EDHOC session.

After verifying the POST request and the C authorization, if everything is correct, the AS responds with the code `'2.01 (Created)'`, which means that the C is authorized, and the AS will provide the access token to the C. Furthermore, alongside the access token, the AS provides the C a set of parameters that allow the C to execute the EDHOC protocol with the RS, which includes information about the RS authorization credential (transported as value or referenced), supported EDHOC methods, or encryption suites. Figure 1 shows the general exchange between a client and the corresponding AS.

Since the access token does not contain secret information, it is only strictly necessary to ensure its integrity and source authentication. Consequently, the AS can protect the access token using either a digital signature or a keyed message digest, using algorithms such as **Message Authentication Code (MAC)** or **Authenticated Encryption with Associated Data (AEAD)**. However, it is also recommended to use a **CBOR Web Token (CWT)** token protected with `COSE_Encrypt/COSE_Encrypt0` as specified in RFC 8392 [11], which allows for secure transport of claims.

Figure 1: General exchange between Client and AS

4.2 Client to Resource Server Communication

This section depicts the interaction between the C, which wants to consume a resource, and the RS, which provides the resource. Consequently, to access the resource, the C must provide

the access token, obtained in the previous step while interacting with the AS, to the RS. In this regard, the C sends a CoAP POST request to the '/authz-info' endpoint of the RS, including the access token in the request, which contains authorization information as well as a PoP method used by the C. Moreover, the C sent this request before the establishment of the security context with EDHOC and OSCORE, which means that the creation of the secure channel will occur after uploading the access token to the RS and will last until the expiration of the access token when the C and the RS must delete the OSCORE Security Context and purge the EDHOC session established between them. Additionally, it is possible to send the access token within an EDHOC message during the key exchange.

After receiving the access token from the C, the RS verifies it before storing it. Verification depends on token encoding (e.g., CWT using COSE, JSON Web Token (JWT) using JSON Object Signing and Encryption (JOSE)), protection, and claims. Additionally, token type also affects verification as self-contained tokens are verified locally, while referenced tokens require AS interaction for claim retrieval. Self-contained tokens must include a verification method proving AS authority. If verification succeeds, the RS stores the token and responds with a 2.01 (Created) code. If there is any error while verifying the access token, the RS must respond with the CoAP code 4.00 (Bad Request) as an error response. Another possible scenario occurs when an access token is valid but later becomes invalid due to expiration or revocation. In this case, the RS must respond with the CoAP code 4.01 (Unauthorized), as well as delete the access token and the OSCORE Secure Context established with the C.

Finally, if C receives the 2.01 code response, it starts the EDHOC and OSCORE Protocol to establish the secure channel with the RS. At this point, C and RS are both authenticated, and from now on C will have access to the resource from RS, while all messages exchanged between C and RS will be protected thanks to the creation of the OSCORE Security Context between them. Figure 2 illustrates this general exchange. As mentioned before, this secure channel will last until the access token used by the C becomes invalid (due to revocation or expiration), which means that the whole process must start again from the beginning.

Figure 2: General exchange between Client and RS

4.3 Architecture

Figure 3: Proposed architecture for the ACE-Framework using EDHOC and OSCORE over NB-IoT

The proposed architecture, shown in Figure 3, integrates **Narrowband Internet of Things (NB-IoT)**, EDHOC, OSCORE, ACE and CoAP protocols. This architecture supports bidirectional communication: uplink communications from end devices to the other two entities and vice versa (downlink). The system comprises end-devices (IoT clients with NB-IoT radio modules), a Radio Access Network (RAN) for long-range communication, a Core network for connectivity services, a Resource Server (RS) for managing protected resources, and an Authorization Server (AS) for security and access control token management.

Key components include: End-device (Raspberry Pi 4 Model B with 1 GB of LPDDR4 RAM); RAN (Radio Access Network); Core Network (4G / 5G core); and RS-Server & AS-Server (Cloud Server Intel Xeon (Skylake, IBRS) processor with two cores running at 2.099GHz, and 2GB of RAM). This stack enables secure, low-power, long-range communication for IoT/Edge devices in constrained environments, leveraging NB-IoT for connectivity and EDHOC/OSCORE/ACE for security. Please note that the RS simulates an IoT device acting as a sensor in the cloud layer instead of being deployed as an IoT device in the IoT layer. The reason is that the tests performed for this study are not focused on performance, which means that the computing capacity of devices is irrelevant. Instead, tests for this study focus on the cybersecurity part of implementing ACE-Framework, EDHOC, and OSCORE for authorized and secure communications in IoT-Edge-Cloud scenarios.

5 Results

The objective of the following tests is to compare the EDHOC, **DTLS**, and **TLS** protocols to evaluate the overhead of these authentication/key-exchange protocols, as well as evaluating OSCORE, DTLS, and TLS for application data protection. The data obtained for DTLS and TLS have been collected from the following theoretical study [12], while the EDHOC and

OSCORE data used are part of the implementation developed in this work.

5.1 Overhead of Key Exchange Protocols

This analysis focuses on comparing key exchange message sizes across protocols under specific standardized conditions. The comparison assumes several key characteristics: an 8-byte ICV (Integrity Check Value) utilizing algorithms like AES_128_CCM.8 or AES-CCM-16-64-128, implementation of either P-256 or Curve25519 curve algorithms and 1-byte lengths for both key identifiers and connection identifiers. The analysis excludes DTLS handshake message fragmentation and only incorporates mandatory (D)TLS extensions to maintain consistency in the comparison. Regarding the EDHOC protocol, it was decided to evaluate the performance of method 0, which uses signature keys for both the initiator and the responder. This method, besides being the one implemented in the scenario, is the most computationally expensive compared to methods based on static keys. Therefore, its comparison is crucial.

Figure 4: Comparison of message sizes in bytes with CCM.8, x25519, and ed25519 or PSK and without Connection ID

Figure 4 shows the sizes in bytes of each of the messages (flights) exchanged during key establishment, as well as the total size of the exchange for each protocol and configuration. The analysis of security protocols reveals significant patterns in message size efficiency. The total message sizes exhibit substantial variation across different protocols, ranging from 280 to 706 bytes, highlighting the importance of protocol selection for specific use cases.

EDHOC proves to be a significantly more efficient alternative compared to other key establishment protocols, especially when considering the context of resource-constrained IoT devices. While traditional protocols like DTLS 1.3 with RPKS and ECDHE require up to 706 bytes in total for message exchange, and TLS 1.3 with similar configurations needs 615 bytes, EDHOC manages to complete key establishment with only 428 bytes, even when using X.509 certificates and ECDHE. This substantial reduction in message size is particularly relevant for IoT devices, where every byte transmitted directly impacts energy consumption and bandwidth usage. Although lighter variants of TLS and DTLS exist using PSK, EDHOC maintains an optimal balance between security and efficiency, offering robust certificate-based authentication with considerably less overhead than its traditional counterparts.

5.2 Overhead for Protection of Application Data

Figure 5: Overhead (8 bytes ICV) in bytes as a function of Connection/Sender ID (Sequence Number = '05')

For the case of OSCORE, the exchange involving the client and the **RS** requesting access to a protected resource and its corresponding response will be considered. This exchange is of particular interest due to its significant impact on the conversation, as it is the most frequently repeated interaction. All overhead calculations in this section will take into account an 8-byte ICV (e.g., AES_128_CCM_8 or AES-CCM-16-64-128), a 6-byte plaintext, and the sequence number '05'. As can be seen in Figure 5, the different protocols generate messages of similar size.

5.3 Discussion

After thoroughly analyzing the results obtained from comparing message sizes and overhead among DTLS, TLS, and EDHOC protocols for key exchange, as well as DTLS, TLS, and OSCORE for application data protection, we discovered several important insights: OSCORE's end-to-end security at the application level is crucial for IoT environments where data traverses multiple, potentially insecure nodes. EDHOC and OSCORE provide enhanced flexibility and adaptability through diverse authentication methods and seamless integration with IoT-specific protocols like COAP, making secure application development and deployment more straightforward. These protocols excel in key management and updates compared to PSK-based approaches, which is essential for large-scale IoT deployments. While their messages may be slightly larger than other options, EDHOC and OSCORE are optimized for minimal memory and processing requirements, making them ideal for resource-constrained IoT devices.

6 Conclusion

This research successfully enhanced secure data sharing across the computing continuum by designing a robust security model addressing resource limitations and challenges in heterogeneous IoT-Edge-Cloud environments. The study confirmed the ACE framework's applicability in resource-constrained scenarios, integrating EDHOC and OSCORE protocols for a unified solution. The rigorous evaluation demonstrated the security robustness, efficiency, and scalability in handling protected data-sharing scenarios from IoT devices to Edge nodes and cloud plat-

forms. These achievements offer a comprehensive, scalable solution for advancing cybersecurity in distributed computing environments.

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